

PREREQUISITES FOR NATURAL APPROACHES IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract

The article analyzes a number of points of ecolinguistics, which are the prerequisites for methodological and conceptual system of household and outside inquire about. Ecolinguistic strategies are highlighted and the issues of ecolinguistics in medially linguistics are sketched out. Specific consideration is paid to the creation of an integrator approach as the premise of orderly biology. The recognizing highlights of environmental worldview appearance within the science of dialect based on the developing slant of ecolinguistics are emphasized. The article bargains with the terms and definitions related with the ecolinguistics, which speak to two fundamental headings:

- 1) ecolinguistics, which thinks about the quality of dialect in terms of human well-being,
- 2) ecolinguistics, which looks at the state of dialect as a dialect framework from the point of view of anthropogenic impact through dialect on the environment.

It is famous that the unused biological worldview shifts the accentuation from people to their interaction with the environment. It is particularly focused that dialect is competent to act as an impacting environment, ie the scale of its vitality and data interaction is very genuine for the encompassing physical environment of the human being. The conclusion is made that an ecolinguistic paradigm should be emphasized within the ponder of dialect science to address the rising issues of the etymological environment in cutting edge society.

Keywords:

ecolinguistics, interlingual and intralingual approaches medially linguistics, translingual viewpoint, media space.

Introduction

Currently, native and foreign scientists are studying the concept of “ecological paradigm”, and many of them are related to the problem of the environmental crisis, features of the development of technogenic civilization, the process of globalization, and threats to the sustainable development of humanity [1].

In this regard, in recent decades there has been a kind of greening of many areas of knowledge, especially in the general content of environmental problems, including environmental history, environmental engineering, ecology, environmental psychology, and includes many other scientific fields.

Each of these disciplines has a distinct body of scientific insight and develops strategies to address the problems it faces, taking into account the disciplinary frameworks, methods, terminology, and concepts of tradition that it has developed.

This is the development of an integrated approach that: This allows us to lay the foundation of a systems ecology. Linguistics is no exception, and scientific areas such as ecolinguistics, which combines linguistics and ecology, are widely developing.

This direction only develops methodological approaches and theoretical possibilities and tries to find problem areas, objects of discussion and points of connection with other

disciplines. Researchers have identified several directions for solving complex and necessary problems of ecolinguistics [2].

Different approaches are classified depending on the criteria prioritized by scientists. The most pressing issue for researchers in this area of ecolinguistics is the issue of violations of spelling norms in the texts of media platforms.

This is mainly due to the simplification and pollution of the language, the inappropriate use of colloquial speech by users of the media space, which, as many scientists note, has led to the problem of illiteracy.

Therefore, one of the goals of our research is to consider the features of the manifestation of the ecological paradigm in linguistics based on new directions in ecolinguistics. To address this issue, we have reviewed some of the basics of ecolinguistics as a methodological and conceptual framework for national and international research from the perspective of an ecological paradigm.

This article discusses some of the basics of the ecolinguistic approach. Its methodological basis is the study of media platforms and related topics.

Research methods and principles

As a result of collecting and summarizing theoretical material using methods of analysis and synthesis, the most famous ecolinguistic approach to the study of problems identified today on some media platforms I came to the conclusion that there are two directions: “symbolic ecology of language” and “natural ecology”.

Our research also includes A.P. Skovorodnikov’s definition of the dichotomous nature of the subject of ecolinguistics. Scientists believe that language is related to the environment and its functions (social factors). The first direction indicates the interdisciplinarity of this subject in the field of linguistics, since it is a complex semiotic system that is influenced by other extralinguistic factors.[3] It is called “The symbolic ecology of language.” This area of research aims to understand how language functions in a particular environment. In an environment made up of other languages and the societies that use them. The interaction between symbolic entities, especially the interaction between language and others, between language and a society that uses language as one of its codes, can be attributed to scientific explanations such as interaction.

This is the social and psychological aspect of linguistic ecology. Thanks to language, certain mental processes occur that have a direct impact on society and its culture. As scientists emphasize, symbolic ecology is not only a matter of preserving languages and their diversity, but also considering the stages of language development and various adaptations to changing environmental conditions and mutations of languages.

This approach assumes the presence of the following aspects: Interlingual and intralingual. The interlinguistic approach takes into account issues related to the habitat

of people speaking a particular ethnic language, the threat of language extinction, the reduction of linguistic diversity in the world, pidginization and creolization of languages.

These studies looked at the characteristics of functionally weak languages that have some degree of weakness, such as narrow applicability, small numbers of native speakers, and the influence of another functionally more competent language.

Intralinguistic aspects of linguistic ecology are rooted in the study of various factors leading to linguistic impoverishment and regression. In this sense, the subject of ecology is the preservation of languages or national languages. The relationship between language and environment is analyzed. The environment consists of the social, cultural and natural conditions necessary to preserve the identity of an ethnic community and its language. For example, the preservation of national culture and traditional areas of activity of indigenous people, speaker, territorial integrity and level of national self-confidence.

Problems of linguistic ecology in this area include the bureaucratization of speech and language, the expansion of borrowings, the vulgarization of oral communication, and the legalization of obscene language. This problem includes semantic distortions in the field of spiritual vocabulary and expressions a break in the cultural tradition of the Russian literary language associated with elements of Church Slavonic, information security, linguistic violence in its various manifestations, etc.

It also includes problems such as the culture of toponyms in the context of historical memory [4]. Intralinguistic aspects study the process of language regression from the perspective of communicative language culture and study violations of logic, clarity and expressiveness of language. There are reasons to talk about aspects beyond language. This involves studying how units of one language (or culture) are used in context and in another language. This aspect is presented in fiction and folklore, and is interpreted in translation practice.

The second approach - the natural ecology of language - is based on the fact that, despite different views on the nature and essence of language, no one denies the existence of language in the material world. Researchers study how language fits into natural ecological contexts such as climate, topography, flora and fauna. There are two points of view on this topic. It is about the study of how natural phenomena are integrated into language and culture and how language influences natural phenomena in the environment. Within this approach, extensive research has been conducted on discourse analysis, the ecology of grammar, indicators of environmental crisis in various policy documents and discourses, and the anthropocentrism of vocabularies [5].

Language acts as a means of influence. In both scientific and everyday contexts, terms such as “information environment”, “language environment”, “text field of language” and “virtual language environment” are increasingly used. These concepts suggest that personality development is influenced by the environment. Scientists have expressed

concern about the state of the language environment and pointed to a direct connection between the language environment and the development of human consciousness, mind and intelligence [6].

An expanded interpretation of the content of ecolinguistics in this sense covers various speech practices and speech works, the information they contain in general, information created through language and used in the information, intellectual and communicative spheres of human activity the important role of everything that is done is the design of its micro- and macroenvironment [7].

The semiotic environment represents the conditions in which people live, are formed and change. This is a dynamically functioning, self-developing text space that influences community members. Examples of such spaces include regional media spaces, place names environments, communication spaces and virtual spaces.

This approach focuses on the problem of establishing environmentally friendly characteristics in relation to complex phenomena, such as: The textual-information environment of communication and its influence on the consciousness of recipients who consume a large number of text messages and live in conditions of universal dialogue. Here we will talk about favorable and unfavorable information environments.

In the first case, the information environment represents the conditions for the development of the subject's information space. In the second case, the information environment suppresses the vital forces and energy of the subject.

The object of protection from this point of view is not only specific individuals, but also professional, social and national groups of people, communities and societies. Some scholars have proposed calling this approach human/social ecology [8].

Main results

Having considered the main directions and research approaches of ecolinguistics, we have identified Problems ecolinguistics in mediallynguistics and determined text media field object fields. Our results correlate with ecolinguistic problems in modern research.

According to the classification of existing approaches, the main questions, solved in this perspective, are: how environmentally friendly informational, speech and text speech of people and what are relationships between people and their information environment life spaces.

Discussion

Research in the field of ecolinguistics was carried out by such scientists as A.P. Skovorodnikov, S.V. Ionova and many others. Researchers have identified differences between the anthropocentric paradigm and the new ecological paradigm by considering synonymous terms (ecolinguistics, ecology of language, "green linguistics"). Similar research is carried out by so-called "green linguistics".

This is part of ecolinguistics, which reconsiders the concept of “garbage” in language, the norms and anomalies of linguistic processes, based on the principle of linguistic diversity within one language. Our study is also an attempt to study violations of spelling norms in the texts of media platforms from the perspective of ecolinguistics, which helps to develop the goals of subject education in accordance with the changing modern socio-cultural conditions.

Conclusion

Based on this, we conclude that linguistics should pay particular attention to research that combines linguistics and ecology. The actions of scientists are aimed at eliminating negative trends in the use of language. The conclusion of the new anthropocentric paradigm is centered around language, pointing to the pressing problems of a linguistic environment that is becoming increasingly unfavorable for humans. Here scientists turn to the bureaucratization of speech and language, the expansion of borrowings, the vulgarization of oral communication, and especially the legalization of swear words that obscure the main meaning of the reported events.

Ecolinguistics currently accumulates only methodological and theoretical capabilities; the search for new data on the real subject of the scientific field and its interaction with other fields is actively underway.

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